

Informing Sustainable Coastal Tourism Management through Carrying Capacity Assessment: The Case of Patuartek Sea Beach

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ABSTRACT

Tourism carrying capacity (TCC) is assessed to determine the maximum number of tourists to be allowed in a tourist destination at a given time. TCC can help control visitor numbers to protect the natural and socio-cultural environment of the destination while ensuring that tourists' needs are met and the well-being of local communities is maintained. Patuartek Beach is one of the most popular sea beaches in Cox's Bazar District, mainly famous for coral stones, sandy beach, and red crabs. However, because of the heavy use of the beach by both local fishermen and tourists, the natural beauty and biodiversity of the beach are under threat of degradation. This study assesses the TCC of Patuartek Beach using the modified Cifuentes Formula incorporating physical, environmental, socio-cultural, economic, and managerial parameters to estimate the optimal number of visitors at Patuartek Beach. The study finds that the effective TCC of Patuartek Beach is 201; that is, the maximum number of tourists should be allowed to enjoy the beach at a given time is 201. The study would facilitate government decision-making by providing an evidence-based guideline for regulating tourist flows at Patuartek Beach, while contributing to the TCC literature supporting sustainable tourism management.

1. Introduction

Assessing tourism carrying capacity (TCC) is not new to destination planning and visitor management. TCC is assessed for managing visitor pressure by determining sustainable visitation limits in popular tourist destinations (Bernal, Montero, & Vázquez, 2024). Around the world, assessing and implementing TCC has been widely recognized and used as a useful tool for balancing tourism growth and sustainability (Hasan et al., 2014). Particularly, in popular island, coastal, and maritime destinations, TCC is widely used to determine the maximum number of tourists that can be accommodated without causing unacceptable ecological degradation, socio-cultural disruption, economic imbalance, or declines in visitor satisfaction (Leka et al., 2025). And, most importantly,

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not assessing and applying TCC in popular tourist destinations may lead to damaging the natural and other attractions of the destination, while causing dissatisfaction among visitors and local communities.

In Bangladesh, although there are a number of very popular destinations, there is rarely any effort to assess and apply visitor limits; notable examples include the TCC assessments conducted for Saint Martin's Island by Hasan et al. (2014) and Inani Beach by Islam et al. (2023). As a result, the natural and cultural attractions of these destinations are often exposed to degradation due to over-tourism, particularly during peak tourism seasons. Due to this over-tourism, while tourist satisfaction declines, local communities sometimes face pressure on their usual living environment, as tourists share the same resource base with them in the destination (Ferdaus et al., 2024).

Patuartek sea beach is a picturesque rocky beach in the Ukhia Upazila of Cox's Bazar district in Bangladesh (Siraz et al., 2023). Patuartek Beach is popularly known for its rocky beach, which is uncommon in Cox's Bazar, as the beach in Cox's Bazar is usually sandy (Islam & Cheng, 2025). Patuartek Beach became very famous among tourists over the past few years. The number of tourists is ever-increasing, particularly after the construction of the Cox's Bazar – Teknaf Marine Drive, as this road gives easy access to this pristine beach. However, uncontrolled tourist arrivals and tourism activities have put pressure on the beach ecosystem, where famous red crabs, endangered sea turtles, birds, and seagrasses are under threat (Islam et al., 2025). Also, as there are only limited facilities available for tourists, the uncontrolled number of tourist arrivals and pressure on those limited facilities have contributed to dissatisfaction among tourists and local community members (Afrin & Sifat, 2023). Therefore, assessing and implementing TCC for the Patuartek Beach is particularly important. This study determines the TCC of Patuartek Sea Beach. The findings of the study would add to our limited knowledge on TCC of the Patuartek Beach, while the government, destination management organisation (DMO), and other stakeholders may gain insights into tourism development and management at Patuartek Beach.

2. Method: The Cifuentes Formula

In this study, the formula proposed by Cifuentes (1992, 1999) has been applied to determine the TCC of Patuartek Beach, Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh. This formula is widely used around the world and has been endorsed by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) and the UN Tourism (Ceballos-Lascuráin, 1996; UNWTO, 1998). This formula has been applied in carrying capacity assessments of several coastal and marine destinations in Bangladesh (Hasan et al., 2014; Islam et al., 2023), Brazil (De Sousa et al., 2014), Costa Rica (Cifuentes, 1992; Cifuentes et al., 1999), Iran (Salemi et al., 2019), Mexico (Segrado Pavón et al., 2015), Portugal (Zacarias et al., 2011), Turkey (Sayan & Atik, 2011), and many other countries (Rodella et al., 2017).

The Cifuentes method considers all relevant site-specific parameters in assessing the TCC of a destination: the maximum number of tourists to be allowed to a destination without deteriorating its natural, economic, social, and cultural environment. This method also considers all site-specific factors affecting the level of tourist satisfaction and local community satisfaction, which are considered limiting factors of the destination. Under this method, the TCC of a destination is assessed through three sequential stages: (i) Physical Carrying Capacity (PCC); (ii) Real Carrying Capacity (RCC); and (iii) Effective Carrying Capacity (ECC).

2.1. Physical Carrying Capacity (PCC)

PCC indicates the maximum number of tourists that a destination or tourist site (e.g., a park, trail, or beach) can physically accommodate within the available space at a given time. The formula for PCC is:

$$PCC = A \times V/a \times Rf$$

Here, A refers to the space available or designated for tourism activities, measured by multiplying the length and width of the area designated for tourism.

For V/a , V represents 'one' tourist, and a refers to the space required by this 'one' tourist to avail the tourism activities comfortably.

Rf , the rotation factor or the number of visitor rotations, refers to the number of acceptable visits during the site's daily operating hours or opening period. Rf is determined by using the following formula:

$$Rf = \text{Daily opening period} \div \text{Average duration of a visit}$$

2.2. Real Carrying Capacity (RCC)

RCC is the maximum acceptable visitor number to be allowed at a tourist destination after relevant *corrective factors* (CFs) are incorporated into the PCC. The RCC is calculated using the formula below:

$$RCC = PCC \times \frac{100 - cf1}{100} \times \frac{100 - cf2}{100} \times \dots \times \frac{100 - cfn}{100}$$

CFs refer to specific attributes or characteristics of a destination and are assessed to identify the negative impacts of tourism activities on the destination. After that, these CFs are adjusted with the PCC to determine the RCC. CF is calculated by:

$$Cf = \frac{M1}{Mt}$$

Here, $M1$ refers to the limiting magnitude of the variable, and Mt represents its total magnitude.

2.3. Effective Carrying Capacity (ECC)

ECC is the final calculated maximum number of visitors that can be permitted at a destination after adjusting the RCC with the destination's *management capacity* (MC). MC refers to the destination management capacity of DMOs and other authorities in terms of infrastructure, financial resources, equipment, and staff required to ensure proper services and security for tourists, as well as the preservation of nature. To determine ECC, MC is adjusted with the RCC:

$$\text{ECC} = \text{RCC} \times \text{MC}$$

3. The Tourist-group Concept

The Cifuentes Formula is primarily based on the minimum spatial distance required between tourists (one tourist and another) to ensure privacy and a comfortable tourism experience. In reality, many tourists come in groups with their families or friends and thus require a comfortable distance from other groups. However, the Cifuentes method does not consider the required distance between groups of tourists (Tran Nghi et al. 2007). Hasan et al. (2014) also argue that although the Cifuentes method considers only the distance between individual tourists when calculating PCC, the necessary distance between tourist groups should also be considered for tourist satisfaction, privacy, and comfort.

To address this limitation of the original formula of Cifuentes, Tran Nghi et al. (2007) considered the distance between tourist groups in determining the carrying capacity of trekking trails in Quang Binh Province in Vietnam. In cases of these trekking trails, Tran Nghi et al. (2007) assumed that tourists are in a single-file line, following one another in sequence. However, in the case of a sea beach, this technique cannot be readily applied as tourists are usually not in lines or queues at a sea beach. Thus, this modified technique provided by Tran Nghi et al. (2007) will not work for calculating the TCC of a sea beach like Patuartek. A new technique has been offered by Hasan et al. (2014), which is appropriate for calculating the TCC of the sea beach. In this technique, the idea of 'distance among groups' is integrated in assessing the carrying capacity of beach-based or similar destinations by slightly modifying the basic Cifuentes formula.

According to the Hasan et al. (2014) technique, each group of tourists is counted as one unit for calculation purposes. For instance, on the sea beach, if an individual tourist requires 4m² space, a group of 4 tourists will require 16m² (4m² × 4) area on the sea beach to maintain the essential distance among themselves within the group. However, if the group needs 2 metres distance from nearby tourist groups, a 1-metre *buffer* should be maintained around each group on all four sides (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Required distance for a group of 4 tourists (Hasan et al., 2014).

In Figure 1, considering the required distance between individual tourists within a group and the distance between tourist groups, the area required by each group will be: $6\text{m} \times 6\text{m} = 36\text{m}^2$. To assess the number of tourist groups that can be permitted on a sea beach, it is required to divide the total beach space by the space required by each tourist group. PCC is then estimated by multiplying the number of tourist groups that can be accommodated simultaneously by the average group size and the rotation factor:

Number of groups allowed:
$$G = \frac{A}{a_g}$$

PCC calculation:
$$PCC = G \times N \times R_f$$

Where:

A = total beach area

a_g = area required per group

G = number of groups

N = number of members per group

R_f = rotation factor

4. Tourism Carrying Capacity of Patuartek Beach

Patuartek Sea Beach is an emerging popular sea beach in Cox's Bazar, located about 32.9 kilometres from Cox's Bazar Airport (Afrin & Sifat, 2023). Currently, it is one of the famous rocky beaches in the Ukhia Upazila of Cox's Bazar (Figure 2). Patuartek Sea Beach features rocky/coral-stone platforms interspersed with sand pockets, tide pools, and a fringe of coastal vegetation. Access is primarily provided via the Marine Drive,

with limited on-site services and emerging informal vendors/activities (e.g., quad bikes, horseback rides). The beach has become a popular stopover along the Cox's Bazar–Teknaf Marine Drive because of its rocky features and the backdrop of green hills. Now, hundreds of visitors crowd the beach, mostly young people, primarily to take photos and make short videos for social media reels. However, due to the increased number of visitors and limited facilities and regulatory monitoring, the natural beauty and biodiversity of the beach are under serious threat of degradation, and therefore require the TCC to be assessed and implemented immediately (Islam et al., 2023).

Figure 2. Real physical area for tourism in Patuateg Beach (Source: Author).

4.1. PCC and RCC of Patuartek Beach

PCC is measured based on the entire physical area of a tourist destination available for tourism use in general. However, the entire area (e.g., beach) cannot be allocated for tourism use considering the economic, socio-cultural, and environmental sustainability issues of the area. Therefore, several *corrective factors (CFs)* (e.g., quicksand or slippery stones on the beach) are considered when assessing the RCC from the PCC. For Patuartek, these corrective factor attributes imply: (CF1) Biodiversity hotspots (e.g., red crab habitats, seagull roosting areas, and sea turtle breeding zones); (CF2) Fish landing area for local communities; (CF3) Rocky unusable area controlled by tides; (CF4) Areas with slip/fall risk on algal stones; (CF5) Sensitivity of intertidal organisms (e.g., crabs, algae, invertebrates) to trampling. Considering these corrective factors based on field survey, a *real physical area* for Patuartek Beach for tourism activities has been assessed by excluding these above-mentioned areas (CF1-CF5) from the beach area (Figure 2 and Table 1).

Table 1. Real Physical Area for Tourism at Patuartek Beach

Beach	Length	Width (average during high tide)	Real Area for Tourism Use
Patuartek	300m	27.26m	8,178m ²

So, the real physical area of Patuartek Beach is 8,178m² (from Table 1). Here, all CFs have already been adjusted in the PCC, and this real physical area will now be used to assess the RCC of Patuartek Beach.

For Patuartek Beach, following TCC parameters have been considered based on the field survey conducted in November 2024:

- a) Space required for each tourist: 4m² (2m × 2m).
- b) Group size on average: 12 tourists in each group.
- c) Distance required between two groups: 6m.
- d) Average duration of tourism activities on the beach: 3 hours.
Daily beach usage period: 6 hours (during daylight high-tide periods).

Therefore, the rotation factor is: $6 \div 3 = 2$.

- e) Space required for each group of 12 tourists makes a rectangle on the beach with 14 metres in length and 12 metres in width (Figure 3). A distance of 6 metres between tourist groups was also considered to ensure comfortable spacing.

Therefore, the space required by a group is: 168m² (14m × 12m).

Figure 3. Area required by each group.

Now, the RCC of Patuartek Beach is calculated as follows:

The *Real Area* for tourism: 8,178m² (from Table 1)

Space needed for each group: 168m²

So, the maximum number of groups to be allowed: $8,178 \div 168 = 48$ groups

So, the RCC of Patuartek = Number of tourist groups \times Average group size \times Rf

$$= 48 \times 12 \times 2$$

$$= 1,152 \text{ visits across two sessions per day}$$

However, these 1,152 tourists cannot visit Patuartek Beach simultaneously, but rather across two daily visitation rotations of three hours each. Therefore, the number of tourists in each session or at a time will be a maximum of $1,152 \div 2$ or 576.

4.2. Effective Carrying Capacity of Patuartek Beach

The ECC of Patuartek Beach was determined based on the current management capacity of DMOs in terms of three broad elements including staff, infrastructure, and equipment (Corbau et al., 2019). A total of 10 corrective factors under these three broad elements were considered to assess the MC score (Table 2).

Table 2. Assessment of the MC Correction Factors.

		Optimum	Max. score	Actual situation at Patuartek Beach	Score
Staff	Lifeguard	Present permanently	1	Absent	0
	Tourist Police	Present permanently	1	Yes, regular police patrolling is conducted along the Marine Drive, but it is not permanent; therefore, the score has been halved.	0.5
Infrastructure	Infrastructure for lifeguards and first aid kits.	At least one	1	Absent	0
	Signage with cautions, Dos and Don'ts, and emergency numbers	At least one	1	Yes, regarding sea turtles and red crabs, to create awareness among tourists. But there is no signage with swimming rules or cautions; therefore, the score has been halved.	0.5
	Public toilets	At least one	1	Washrooms are available in nearby restaurants that tourists use, but there is no public toilet. Therefore, the score has been halved.	0.5
	Beach chair for hire	As per tourists' demand	1	Depends on the season: available only in the peak tourist season in winter; therefore, the score has been halved.	0.5
	Tourist lounge with prayer room	At least one	1	Absent	0
Equipment	CC-cameras and other surveillance equipment	At least one	1	Beachside restaurants have their own CC cameras, but there is	0.5

				no surveillance equipment installed by law enforcement agencies. Therefore, the score has been halved.	
	Communication devices (e.g., telephone, walkie-talkie)	At least one	1	Yes	1
	First aid kits	At least one	1	Absent	0
Sum			10		3.5
MC score			1		0.35

Based on the calculation in Table 2, the MC score for Patuartek Beach is 0.35. Therefore, the ECC of Patuartek Beach is 403 ($1,152 \times 0.35$) tourists per day across two sessions. But again, these 403 tourists cannot visit Patuartek Beach at the same time, but are distributed into two sessions (as $R_f=2$). Therefore, the number of tourists to be allowed in each session or at a time is $403 \div 2$ or a maximum of 201.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

Considering physical site constraints, environmental sensitivity, local livelihood use, and tourist safety considerations, the RCC, or the real number of tourists that can be accommodated at Patuartek Beach at a given time, was estimated to be 576 tourists. Although the physical space of the beach could potentially accommodate more visitors, the environmental sensitivity of the rocky coastal ecosystem, areas used by local fishermen for fish landing, and zones with slip and fall risks due to algal-covered stones significantly reduce the real carrying capacity of Patuartek Beach (Butler, 2020). On top of that, when managerial parameters, including staff, infrastructure, and equipment, were taken into consideration to estimate the ECC, based on the MC score of 0.35 (see Table 2), the optimal number of visitors at Patuartek Beach was found to be 201. This relatively low destination management capacity reflects: (i) limited or no safety and security services, including tourist police and lifeguard services; (ii) very limited or no infrastructure, such as washrooms, a tourist lounge with a prayer room, shaded structures for lifeguards, and emergency first-aid kits; and (iii) a lack of surveillance and communication equipment currently available at the site.

The result, therefore, indicates that if management capacities or MCs can be improved by the governments, DMOs, and other stakeholders, the ECC of a destination can increase significantly (Mexa & Coccossis, 2017). For example, with the improvement in management capacity at Patuartek, which has a score of only 0.35 now, the TCC will increase significantly. Therefore, one of the key strategic responses to increase the current TCC of Patuartek Beach is to strengthen management capacity. For instance,

improvements in infrastructure, tourist facilities and services, and monitoring systems could increase the management capacity in the future, and the TCC of Patuartek Beach could even double its current level. Therefore, one limitation of this study is that the TCC was estimated only for a specific period of time (November 2024); thus, the TCC derived in this study may change over time due to variations in management capacity and the overall conditions of the destination (Santos & Brilha, 2023). Since the TCC of a destination is dynamic and may evolve, it should be reassessed periodically to accommodate such changes.

References

- Afrin, M., and A. Sifat. 2023. "Preserving the Shoreline: A Potential Approach of Eco-Architecture on the Seacoast of Bay of Bengal." In *Proceedings of the International Conference of Contemporary Affairs in Architecture and Urbanism (ICCAUA)* 6 (1): 742–48.
- Bernal, B., N. Montero, and S. Vázquez. 2024. "A Comparative Study of the Tourism Carrying Capacity of the State of Baja California between 2019 and 2022." *Sustainability* 16 (10): 3938. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16103938>.
- Butler, R. W. 2020. "Tourism Carrying Capacity Research: A Perspective Article." *Tourism Review* 75 (1): 207–11. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TR-05-2019-0194>.
- Ceballos-Lascuráin, H. 1996. *Tourism, Ecotourism, and Protected Areas: The State of Nature-Based Tourism around the World and Guidelines for Its Development*. Gland, Switzerland: IUCN. <https://doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.CH.1996.7.en>.
- Cifuentes, M. 1992. *Determinación de Capacidad de Carga Turística en Áreas Protegidas*. Turrialba, Costa Rica: CATIE.
- Cifuentes, M., C. A. B. Mesquita, J. Méndez, M. E. Morales, and N. Aguilar. 1999. *Capacidad de Carga Turística de las Áreas de Uso Público del Monumento Nacional Guayabo, Costa Rica*. Turrialba, Costa Rica: WWF.
- Corbau, C., G. Benedetto, P. P. Congiatu, U. Simeoni, and D. Carboni. 2019. "Tourism Analysis at Asinara Island (Italy): Carrying Capacity and Web Evaluations in Two Pocket Beaches." *Ocean & Coastal Management* 169: 27–36.
- De Sousa, R. C., L. C. Pereira, R. M. da Costa, and J. A. Jiménez. 2014. "Tourism Carrying Capacity on Estuarine Beaches in the Brazilian Amazon Region." *Journal of Coastal Research* 70: 545–50.
- Ferdaus, J., M. S. Islam, M. K. Momo, and M. K. Hassan. 2024. "Integrating Climate Change in Coastal and Maritime Tourism Development in Bangladesh." *Bangladesh Maritime Journal* 8 (1): 125–43. <https://doi.org/10.70279/bmj-v8-i1-1038>.
- Hasan, S. R., M. K. Hassan, and M. S. Islam. 2014. "Tourist-Group Consideration in Tourism Carrying Capacity Assessment: A New Approach for Saint Martin's Island, Bangladesh." *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development* 5 (19): 150–58.
- Islam, M. S., M. K. Momo, and K. Hassan. 2023. "Determining Tourism Carrying Capacity of Inani Beach, Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh." *Bangladesh Maritime Journal* 7 (1): 137–52. <https://doi.org/10.70279/bmj-v7-i1-1047>.

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- Islam, M. Z., S. M. Sharf-Ul-Alam, Z. N. Keya, M. Jannat, Z. Alam, Z. F. Khan, A. Maitra, and M.A.S. Khan. 2025. "Pathways and Experiences of Children in Beach Vending: Findings from Cox's Bazar Sea Beach in Bangladesh." *Public Health Challenges* 4 (4): e70163. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/puh2.70163>
- Islam, T., and H. Cheng. 2025. "Occurrence and Risk Assessment of Microplastics Pollution in the World's Longest Natural Beach, Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh." *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution* 236 (5): 316.
- Leka, A., A. Lagarias, M. Panagiotopoulou, and A. Stratigea. 2022. "Development of a Tourism Carrying Capacity Index (TCCI) for Sustainable Management of Coastal Areas in Mediterranean Islands: Case Study Naxos, Greece." *Ocean & Coastal Management* 216: 105978.
- Mexa, A., and H. Coccossis. 2017. "Tourism Carrying Capacity: A Theoretical Overview." In *The Challenge of Tourism Carrying Capacity Assessment*, 53–70.
- Rodella, I., C. Corbau, U. Simeoni, and K. Utizi. 2017. "Assessment of the Relationship between Geomorphological Evolution, Carrying Capacity and Users' Perception: Case Studies in Emilia-Romagna (Italy)." *Tourism Management* 59: 7–22.
- Salemi, M., S. A. Jozi, S. Malmasi, and S. Rezaian. 2019. "A New Model of Ecological Carrying Capacity for Developing Ecotourism in the Protected Area of the North Karkheh, Iran." *Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing* 47 (11): 1937–47.
- Santos, P. L., and J. Brilha. 2023. "A Review on Tourism Carrying Capacity Assessment and a Proposal for Its Application on Geological Sites." *Geoheritage* 15 (2): 47.
- Sayan, M. S., and M. Atik. 2011. "Recreation Carrying Capacity Estimates for Protected Areas: A Study of Termessos National Park." *Ekoloji* 20 (78): 66–74. <https://doi.org/10.5053/ekoloji.2011.7811>.
- Segrado Pavón, R. G., L. Arroyo Arcos, K. Amador Soriano, M. Palma Polanco, and R. D. C. Serrano Barquín. 2015. "Hacia un Modelo de Aprovechamiento Turístico Sustentable en Áreas Naturales Protegidas: Estudio de Caso del Parque Natural Chankanaab de Cozumel, Mexico." *PASOS Revista de Turismo y Patrimonio Cultural* 13 (1): 25–42.
- Siraz, M. M. M., M. H. Kamal, Z. H. Khan, M. S. Alam, J. Al Mahmud, M. B. Rashid, M. U. Khandaker, H. Osman, and S. Yeasmin. 2023. "Evaluation of Radioactivity in Soil and Rock Samples from an Undiscovered Sea Beach in the Southeastern Coastline of Bangladesh and Associated Health Risk." *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 195 (9): 1028. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-023-11636-5>
- Tran, N., T. L. Nguyen, D. T. Nguyen, M. Dang, and X. T. Dinh. 2007. "Tourism Carrying Capacity Assessment for Phong Nha-Ke Bang and Dong Hoi, Quang Binh Province." *VNU Journal of Science, Earth Sciences* 23: 80–87.
- UNWTO. 1998. *Guide for Local Authorities on Developing Sustainable Tourism*. Madrid: World Tourism Organization.
- Zacarias, D. A., A. T. Williams, and A. Newton. 2011. "Recreation Carrying Capacity Estimations to Support Beach Management at Praia de Faro, Portugal." *Applied Geography* 31 (3): 1075–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2011.01.020>.